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Stability Constants of N-(2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene)-4-Carbomethoxyaniline with Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cd^{2+}

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In the present communication the successive stability constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of the complexes of N-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene)-4-carbomethoxyaniline with some transition metals ions are described.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and methyl ester of *p*-aminobenzoic acid in ethanol. The product was repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure compound, m.p. 171°.

All measurements were carried out at 30 ± 0.1 . The pH meter used was Elico Model LI 15 with glass electrode designed for use over the pH 0.0 to 11.0 in combination with the dip type calomel electrode. The experimental details and computational methods were the same as described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

The ligand used in this study did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during titration and by the absence of any significant drift in the pH even after 1 hr.

In the ligand, it is the phenolic (OH) group that takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation the number of dissociable protons, Y, attached to each ligand molecule is one.

A curve between B values (pH meter readings) and corresponding $\bar{n}_A$ values was plotted (Fig. 1) and the value of pK_1^H was evaluated from the half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. The plot of $\log (\bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A))$ vs B was also drawn. From this pK_1 was evaluated. This value agrees quite well with that obtained by half integral method.

The $\log K_1$ value for Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Cd^{2+} systems were determined by half integral method, plotting the $\bar{n}$ values against pL (Fig. 2). These

Fig. 1. Formation curve of N-[2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene]-4-carbomethoxyaniline.

values were further confirmed by the plots of $\log (\bar{n}/(1-\bar{n}))$ against pL . For Cu^{2+} system $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were computed by least squares method. The order of bivalent metal chelates was found to be $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+}$ which was in agreement with Mellor and Maley² order. The values are reported in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Metal ligand systems of N-[2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene]-4-carbomethoxyaniline.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SOME COMPLEXES OF N-(2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHALIDENE)-4-CARBOMETHOXYANILINE

	$t = 30 \pm 0.1^\circ$				
	H^+	Cu^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Cd^{2+}
$\log K_1$	8.76	7.76	5.08	4.78	4.14
$\log K_2$	—	6.84	—	—	—

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